

STRYCHNINE AND BRUCINE. PART VI.

MONONITROSTRYCHNINE

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Mononitrostrychnine is prepared from strychnine nitrate and gives aminostrychnine on reduction. Both bases give crystalline salts and the nitro group is unaffected by acid and alkaline hydrolysis. Mononitrostrychnine, monoaminostrychnine and some salts have been tested for fungicidal activity with negative results.

The action of nitric acid on strychnine (*Gazzetta*, 1878, 8, 82; *Ber.*, 1881, 14, 774; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1907, 75, 122; *Compt. rend.*, 1883, 96, 585; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1885, 47, 139; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 152) has been the subject of a number of publications as a result of which a number of products have been characterised, which have contributed their part in the elucidation of the constitution of strychnine molecule. Tafel's dinitrostrychnine hydrate nitrate (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 333; *Annalen*, 1898, 301, 285) was proved by Siddiqui (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sc.*, 1940, 11A, 268) to be dinitrostrychnic acid. In connection with this work a publication of Loebisch and Schoop (*Monatsh*, 1885, 6, 844), attracted the attention which describes the preparation of mononitrostrychnine and its conversion into an isomer on treatment with alcoholic potassium hydroxide. From this it appears that the isomer is mononitrostrychnic acid which furnishes a potassium salt and is formed by the cleavage of the cyclic amide group of the strychnine molecule.

To decide this a study of the substance was undertaken.

In this investigation mononitrostrychnine has been prepared from strychnine nitrate which gives monoaminostrychnine, m. p. 280°, on reduction. Both the bases give crystalline salts. Mononitrostrychnine in acid solution on basification with sodium and potassium hydroxides give their salts and the base is only recovered when the solution is neutralised with ammonia or sodium carbonate. The formation of alkali salts is a peculiar behaviour and resembles those of nitrophenols. The bases from the alkali salts are obtained by a method described under experimental. Mononitrostrychnine is not isomerised by treatment with alcoholic potassium hydroxide but gives a base identical with it. The nitro group is firmly bound and is unaffected by acid and alkaline hydrolysis. The exclusive formation of one mononitrostrychnine from strychnine nitrate is a case of migration of the nitro group from the basic nitrogen (b) to some place in the molecule while its stability points to its substitution in the benzene nucleus but at the same time other possibilities cannot be ruled out and the exact position

will only be fixed by degradative experiments. In dinitrostrychnine the nitro group occupy positions 5 and 7 of the benzene nucleus as proved by Robinson and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 830; 1931, 733; 1932, 780; 1933, 486), and if in this case also the nitro group enters the nucleus then it appears probable that it occupies position 5 and we have to visualise the strychnine molecule in such a way that the pyrrolidine nucleus containing the basic N (b) is so orientated or folded round an axis due to its dynamic condition that the linkages are not disturbed and the *trans* configuration of the two nuclei containing the basic N (b) and the non-basic N (a) is maintained and that it offers a closer proximity for migration or jumping of the nitro group from the basic N (b) to position 5 of the benzene nucleus.

Mononitrostrychnine, its hydrochloride and the potassium salt, aminostrychnine and its hydrochloride were also tested for fungicidal activity by the spore germination test (*vide* Experimental). There was 89-100 percent germination while in solution mononitrostrychnine, monoaminostrychnine and its hydrochloride in 1 : 1000 concentration some mould was found to grow profusely. It appears probable that in low concentrations strychnine does not act as a germicidal to fungi.

EXPERIMENTAL

Strychnine Nitrate.—Dilute nitric acid (2% and 4%) was used when the former was found better as the latter gave increased yield of dinitrostrychnine. Strychnine (50 g.) was dissolved in dilute nitric acid (2%, 400 c.c.) by warming on the water-bath. Undissolved strychnine was filtered and the filtrate on cooling deposited strychnine nitrate in needles. The filtrate from this was used again to dissolve undissolved strychnine till it all went into solution, yield 50 g. (81%). The nitrate is soluble in water and chars at 280°. The mother-liquor from the nitrate on evaporation to dryness on the water-bath gave dinitrostrychnine (9 g.) which on reduction with zinc and hydrochloric acid yielded diaminostrychnine, m.p. 287° and gave no depression with an authentic specimen (Siddiqui, m.p. 287°; Hanriot, m.p. 265°, Leuchs and Krönke, m.p. not below 300°).

Mononitrostrychnine and its Salts.—Strychnine nitrate (33 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (330 g.) by maintaining a temperature below 20°. The red solution after keeping for 8 days was diluted with water (80 parts) and was then made alkaline with ammonia when it yielded the precipitate of mononitrostrychnine.

chnine which was washed with water, yield 29 g. (93%). It crystallises from acetone in prisms, m.p. 245° (Loebisch, m.p. 225°). In a second preparation basification of the solution was done with sodium hydroxide (30% aqueous solution) when a yellow precipitate appeared which dissolved in water on washing. The solution after making acid with hydrochloric acid (10%) was evaporated to dryness and the residue was taken up in dilute acetic acid (10%). The solution on neutralisation with aqueous sodium hydroxide gave a deep yellow precipitate which dissolved very little in chloroform and benzene (soluble fraction in prisms was identical with mononitrostrychnine). To recover the base from the yellow sodium salt it was dissolved in alcoholic hydrochloric acid and refluxed for 1 hour on the water-bath when sodium chloride separated which was filtered. The solution was further refluxed for 2 hours. The solvent was then removed and the residue was dissolved in water and the clear solution was divided into two portions, one being neutralised with ammonia and the other with sodium carbonate solution, the products from both were identical with mononitrostrychnine. It is soluble in acetone, benzene and alcohol and readily in chloroform. The combined fractions were fractionally recrystallised into six fractions when first two melted at 245° and the next two at 243-44°, the fraction fifth at 242° and the last at 238° and none gave any depression on admixture. The mother-liquor on complete removal of the solvent yielded a negligible quantity of an impure base which decomposed below 200°. (Found in material dried at 100°: C, 66.91; H, 6.00; N, 10.8. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_2 \cdot NO_2$: C, 66.49; H, 5.54; N, 11.08 per cent).

The hydrochloride was obtained by adding ethereal hydrogen chloride to a solution of the base in chloroform. It was soluble in acetone, alcohol and water and crystallised from alcohol-ether in light yellow needles, which shrink and stick to the sides at 250°.

The picrate in benzene solution was obtained as an amorphous powder. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and water. It chars and has no definite m.p. below 300°. [Found in substance dried at 100°: N, 12.8. $C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_2NO_2 \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires N, 13.8 per cent].

The chloroplatinate was obtained as a cream-coloured powder on mixing aqueous solution of the hydrochloride and the platinic chloride. It is insoluble in alcohol and water and does not melt below 300°. [Found in anhydrous material: Pt, 17.73. $(C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_2 \cdot NO_2 \cdot HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 17.6 per cent].

The aurichloride was prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of gold chloride and the hydrochloride as a yellow powder. It is soluble in acetone and has m.p. 242° (decomp.). (Found in material dried at 100°: Au, 28.4. $C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_2 \cdot NO_2 \cdot HCl \cdot AuCl_3$ requires Au, 27.4 per cent).

The Nitrate—To an alcoholic solution of the base an alcohol-ether solution of nitric acid was added when the nitrate came down in needles which do not melt below 300°. It is soluble in water and difficultly in alcohol.

Attempted Hydrolysis of Mononitrostrychnine with Alcoholic-Potassium hydroxide.—Mononitrostrychnine was refluxed with 25% alcoholic potassium hydroxide on a sand-bath for 25 hours. The bright red solution on concentration gave ruby-red crystals which become yellow on complete removal of the solvent. The salt was refluxed with alcoholic hydrochloric acid (10%) for 6 hours and the separated potassium chloride was filtered. The solvent was removed and the residue was dissolved in water. The clear solution on basification with ammonia gave a base, m.p. 245° which gave no depression when mixed with mononitrostrychnine. This shows the stability of the nitro group. The nitro group is not removed on treatment with alkali nor the cyclic amide group is ruptured by this treatment. The experiment further shows that the alkali treatment does not isomerise mononitrostrychnine and the product obtained on reduction yields monoaminostrychnine.

Reduction of Mononitrostrychnine: Monoaminostrychnine.—The various fractions were reduced but in every case an identical product was obtained. Nitrostrychnine (0.9 g.) with zinc and hydrochloric acid (50 c.c., 50%) was slightly warmed on the water-bath. When brisk evolution of hydrogen commenced the mixture was removed from the water-bath. The reduction was complete in 15 minutes. The solution was filtered and decomposed with sodium hydroxide (30%). The precipitate and the filtrate were shaken with chloroform. The solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent monoaminostrychnine crystallised in glistening plates, m.p. 280° (Leobisch, m.p. 275°). When the solution after reduction was not worked up at once and was allowed to stand, the base was coloured and the impurity was got rid of with great difficulty. (Found in material dried at 100°: C, 71.91; H, 6.76; N, 11.91. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_2 \cdot NH_2$: C, 72.2; H, 6.59; N, 12.03 per cent).

The dihydrochloride was prepared by adding chloroform solution of the base to an excess of hydrogen chloride in ether when it came down as a sticky precipitate. It crystallised from alcohol-ether in long needles with a violet tinge, and does not melt below 300°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone and water.

The chloroplatinate separated in aggregates of needles with a brownish tinge on mixing an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride and platinic chloride. It does not melt below 300°. On warming a pinch in water a pink to violet solution is produced. [Found in material dried at 100°: Pt, 25.4. $(C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_2 \cdot NH_2 \cdot 2HCl)_2 \cdot 2PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 25.7 per cent].

The dipicrate separated when chloroform solution of the base was added to a solution of picric acid in chloroform-ether. It was well washed with ether and crystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether in red needles, m.p. 265°. It is soluble in acetone, chloroform, alcohol and water. [Found in material dried at 100°: N, 15.6. $C_{21}H_{21}O_2NH_2 \cdot 2 [C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)]$ requires N, 15.83 per cent].

Fungicidal properties.—Fungicidal properties of the following five substances were tested by the Imperial Mycologist by the spore germination test. Viable

spores of *Ustilago kollerii* Wille were used for the purpose. The results are given below.

Concentrations

Substance.	1 : 500	1 : 1000	1 : 2500	1 : 5000	1 : 7500
A. Mononitrostrychnine ...	97	97	100	98	100% germination
B. Mononitrostrychnine hydrochloride ...	89	94	99	99	99% ..
C. Potassium salt of mononitrostrychnine ...	93	96	98	99	100% ..
D. Monoaminostrychnine hydrochloride ...	94	94	90	98	100% ..
E. Monoaminostrychnine ...	97	93	98	99	99% ..

B, C, and D were dissolved in water and A and E in dilute acetic acid and all were diluted with water. In solution of A, D and E in 1 : 1000 concentration some mould was actually found to grow profusely.

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